

KNOWLEDGE ORGANIZATION IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

(I-KOAL 2015)

(Digital India-Digital Libraries)

Editors

Salek Chand
M Natarajan
R N Malviya

Integration of Human Factors in Networked Information A Special Issue of the Traditional Libraries to Digital Environment

Dr. Krishna Kumar Kesharwani

Assistant Librarian

Central Library

Dr. Bhim Rao Ambedkar University, Agra (U.P.) 282 002

Mobile Nos. 09926377466 & 07599117491

E-mail ID : kesharwani67@gmail.com

&

Prabhat Singh Thakur

Librarian

BTIRT Sagar (M.P.) 470 004

Mobile No. 09826234300

E-mail ID : thakurprabhat14@gmail.com

Abstract:

With the advancement of the World Wide Web, networked computing has become an essential determinant on how people access and exchange information. The integration of human factors in networked information has the intrinsic goal of improving the effectiveness of computer-to-human interaction and, ultimately, of human-to-human communication. Information and communication technology (ICT) has revolutionized the concept of libraries. Each and every library is slowly getting digitized. A 'digital library' comprises digital collections, services and infrastructure to support lifelong learning, research, scholarly communication as well as preservation and conservation of our recorded knowledge. It is also a process of democratization of information. This article will discuss the factors that will necessitate the traditional libraries to get digitized, as well as the definition, need, advantages and disadvantages of digital libraries, the requirement for building a digital library etc.

Keywords : Human factors, Human Computer Interaction, Computer Security, Digital Libraries, Information Systems.

INTRODUCTION

We are in the age of a networked society where information and communication technology (ICT) in addition to its use in all spheres of human activity has been used extensively to record, store, and disseminate the information in the digital form. Information and communication technology (ICT) has almost converted the world into a global village. The revolution in the ICT sector is influencing the information industry also. Libraries are also

changing to meet the demand put on them. The new generation whose demand for information is never met is always demanding that traditional libraries should be developed as a well equipped and interconnected as digital libraries.

The term Digital Library has a variety of potential meanings, ranging from a digitized collection of material that one might find in a traditional library through to the collection of all digital information along with the services that make that information useful to all possible users. As there are many definitions of a "digital library," terms such as "electronic library" and "virtual library" are often used synonymously. A digital library is nothing but a large database for the people who are working on hypertext environment. It is an environment, which supports the full life cycle of creation, storage, preservation, dissemination and use of data, information and knowledge.

Origin and Development of Human Factors

Frederick Taylor (1911) employed technologies and methods developed in the late 19th century—photography, moving pictures, and statistical analysis—to improve work practices. Time-and-motion studies were successful with assembly line manufacturing and other manual tasks. Despite the uneasiness with —Taylorism reflected in Charlie Chaplin's popular satire *Modern Times*, science and engineering continued to pursue gains in efficiency.

The World Wars accelerated these efforts, matching people to jobs, training them, and then designing equipment and jobs to be more easily mastered. Engineering psychology was born during World War II after it was found that simple flaws in the design of aircraft controls (Roscoe, 1997) and escape hatches (Dyson, 1979) led to aircraft losses and thousands of casualties. After the war, American aviation psychologists created the Human Factors Society. Two legacies of the conflict were respect for the potential of computing, based on its use in code breaking, and enduring interest in behavioral requirements for design. For more on this period, see Roscoe (1997) and Meister (1999, 2005).

Early tool use, whether by assembly line workers or pilots, was not discretionary. If training was necessary, people were trained. One research goal was to reduce training time, but more important was to increase the speed and reliability of skilled performance.

History of Human Computer Interaction

Information may have persistent qualities, but technologies fade away. For most of the computing era, interaction involved 80-column punch cards, paper tape, line editors, 1920-character displays, 1-megabyte diskettes, and other extinct species. Are the interaction issues of those times relevant today? No.

On the other hand, aspects of the psychology of human-computer interaction change more slowly, or not at all. Much of what was learned about perceptual, cognitive, social, and emotional processes in interacting with older technologies applies to emerging technologies. But there, history is of less interest than what was learned.

Nevertheless, the rapid pace of change strengthens some reasons for understanding aspects of the field's history:

1. Although several disciplines are engaged in human-computer interaction research and application, few people are exposed to more than one. By seeing how the others evolved, we can identify benefits in expanding our focus, as well as obstacles to doing so.
2. The recognition of past visionaries and innovators is part of building a community and inspiring future contributors, even when specific past achievements are difficult to appreciate today.
3. Some visions and prototypes were quickly converted to widespread application, others took decades, and some remain unrealized. By understanding the reasons for different outcomes, we might assess today's visions more realistically.
4. Crystal balls are notoriously unreliable, but anyone planning or managing a career in a rapidly-changing field must consider the future. One thing is certain: It won't resemble the present. Our best chance to anticipate change is to find trajectories that extend from the past through the present.

This account is not an engineering history that emphasizes —firsts. It focuses on when technologies and practices became widely used, as reflected in the spread of systems and applications. This is often accompanied by disciplinary development, formalized in the growth of associations and research fields. More social history than conceptual history, this survey points to trends and trajectories that you might download into your crystal balls.

A central theme is the impact of successive waves of hardware innovation, —Moore's Law broadly construed. This familiar phenomenon, unexamined in previous HCI histories, is essential to discussing disciplines and associations, which often sprang up around a new technology and withered or died when it was replaced. In addition, hardware costs had to drop for some applications to become practical. Conceptual histories pass over these factors. For example, graphical user interface concepts were invented early in the era of transistor-based computers. Conceptual development progressed slowly over the next half century. But only in the mid-1980s were widely-available computers powerful enough to devote that much memory and processing to supporting interaction.

In terms of broad movements, the HCI threads within Human Factors, Information Systems, and Computer Science quickly expanded from narrow user bases to embrace broad constituencies. This is less true of technology use in Information Science and its predecessors. Until more recently the latter remained focused on narrower target audiences—librarians, document managers in business and government agencies, scientists and engineers, and other specialists. Nevertheless, the early history enables us to understand the developments in recent decades, when broad HCI concerns became significant in information studies.

An historical account is a perspective. It emphasizes some things while deemphasizing or omitting others. A history can be wrong in details, but is never right in any final sense. Your questions and interests determine whether or not a perspective is useful to you.

A blueprint for intellectual histories of HCI was established by Ron Baecker in the opening chapters of the 1987 and 1995 editions of *Readings in Human-Computer Interaction*. Brian Shackel's (1997) account of European contributions and specialized

essays by Brad Myers (1998) on HCI engineering history and Alan Blackwell (2006) on the history of metaphor in design added insights and references. Perlman et al. (1995) is a compendium of HCI papers that appeared in the Human Factors literature through 1994. HCI research within Management Information Systems is covered in Banker and Kaufmann (2004). Burke (1998) is an example of a focused study of a digital effort within Information Science.

A wave of popular and scholarly books have addressed the history of personal computing, which is part of this account (e.g. Hiltzik, 1999; Bardini, 2000; Hertzfeld, 2005; Markoff, 2005). This chapter expands on Grudin (2005; 2006, 2008). Historical topics are also present in the Timelines column of ACM Interactions from March 2006 through the present, including several of direct relevance to Information Science.

Definition of Digital Libraries

"According to William Arms a digital library is a managed collection of information, with associated services, where the information is stored in digital formats and accessible over a network. A crucial part of this definition is that the information is managed. A stream of data sent to earth from a satellite is not a library. The same data, when organized systematically, becomes a digital library collection. Most people would not consider a database containing financial records of one company to be a digital library, but would accept a collection of such information from many companies as part of a library. Digital libraries contain diverse information for use by many different users. Digital libraries range in size from tiny to huge. They can use any type of computing equipment and any suitable software. The unifying theme is that information is organized on computers and available over a network, with procedures to select the material in the collections, to organize it, to make it available to users, and to archive it."

There are many definitions of a "digital library." Terms such as "electronic library" and "virtual library" are often used synonymously. The elements that have been identified as common to these definitions are:

1. The digital library is not a single entity;
2. The digital library requires technology to link the resources of many;
3. The linkages between the many digital libraries and information services are transparent to the end users;
4. Universal access to digital libraries and information services is a goal;
5. Digital library collections are not limited to document surrogates: they extend to digital artifacts that cannot be represented or distributed in printed formats.

Changes from Traditional Library to Virtual Library

The development is already taking place. The traditional closed access libraries are change towards open access library. The open access libraries are change towards automated library, the automated one towards the electronics, the electronics to digital and finally end in digital library and its different aspect/badan barman virtual library. Is it really true? The truth is that nobody knows what will be the future of libraries. In the following Para an attempt has been made to categorized the different types of libraries based on the

technology used. It's the best time to mention that there is no strict line of demarcation between the latter four types of libraries.

1. **Traditional library:** The collection of the traditional libraries is mostly print media, manuscripts etc and are not well organized. The document are deteriorating at a rapid rate, the collection information is not easy to locate and so does not easily reach to user, Again the traditional libraries are confined itself within a physical boundary.
2. **Automated library:** A library with machine-readable catalog, computerized acquisition, circulation and OPAC are called as automated library. The holding of this type of libraries are same as that of traditional libraries.
3. **Electronics library:** When automated libraries goes for LAN (Local Area Networking) and CD-ROM networking and started procuring E- journal and other similar kind of publication then it is known as electronic library. The resources of the electronic libraries are in both print and electronic form. The electronic Medias are used for storage retrieval and delivery of information.
4. **Digital library:** It is a later stage of electronic library. In digital library high speed optical fiber are used for LAN and the access is over WAN and provide a wide range of Internet based services i.e. audio and video conferencing and like other. The majority of the holding of a digital library is in the computer readable form and also acts as a point of access to other on line sources.
5. **Hybrid library:** The libraries, which are working both in electronic or digital and print environment, are known as hybrid library. Actually it is a transitional state between print and digital environment. It is estimated that in near future libraries will be of hybrid nature, some of the very strong point in favor of this view are centuries old reading habit of paper, convenience of handling and reading a paper document then the digitized one (in case of digitized some equipment are must needed to read the document), incompatible standard of electronic product, different display standard of digital product and its associated problem etc.

Factors of digital libraries

The limited buying power of libraries, complex nature of recent document, storage problem etc are some of the common factor which are influencing to change to digital mode, some other factors are:

1. Information explosion
2. Searching problem in traditional libraries
3. Low cost of technology: When we consider the storage capacity of digital document and its maintained then it can be easily realize that the cost of technologies is much more less than that of traditional libraries.
4. Environmental factor: the use of digital libraries is the cleanest technologies to fulfill the slogan "Burn a CD-ROM save a tree"
5. New generation needs

Requirement of digital libraries

The Internet and World Wide Web provide the impetus and technological environment for the development and operation of a digital library. The Internet provides the TCP/IP and or its associated protocol for accessing the information and web provide tools and technique for publishing the information over Internet. In the digital environment it is reasonable to say that a central back up or archive should be created at the national level, which will store information out put of the region as well as information from out-side the country. Some of the requirement for a digital libraries are:

1. **Audio visual** : Color T.V., V.C.R., D.V.D., Sound box, Telephone etc.
2. **Hardware** : Computer, Server, P.C. with multimedia, U.P.S. etc
3. **Software**: Any suitable software, which is interconnected and suitable for LAN and WAN connection. PC Pandi
4. **Network**: LAN, MAN, WAN, Internet etc.
5. **Printer**: Laser printer, Dot matrix, Barcode printer, Digital graphic printer etc
6. **Scanner**: H.P. Scan jet, flatbed, Sheet feeder, Drum scanner, Slide scanner, Microfilming scanner, Digital camera, Barcode scanner etc
7. **Storage devices**: Optical storage device, CD-ROM, Jukebox etc.

Sources of a digital library

The sources of a digital library are those, which the computer can store, organized, transmit and display without any intervening conversion process. It includes both print and electronic or digital material. The digital material may be of multimedia types or any other i.e. only digital audio, video, full text information, photographs, drawings, digitized sounds, e-books, v-books, e-journals, electronic tax, maps, images, 3D representation etc. The collection may also include structured /unstructured text, scanned images, graphic audios, video recordings etc

On line sources:

1. Local database of traditional books in machine-readable form.
2. E-book, v-book, electronic tax, map, image, sound, video, and multimedia etc.
3. E-journal
4. LAN, MAN, WAN for web browsing, e- mail etc.
5. Well trained manpower for online help

Off line sources:

1. C.D-ROM, Jukebox etc.
2. Audio visual aid etc.

Advantages of the Digital Library

A digital library is not confined to a particular location or so called building it is virtually distributed all over the world. The user can get his/ her information on his own computer screen by using the Internet. Actually it is a network of multimedia system, which provides fingertip access. The spoken words or the graphical display of a digital library is again having a different impact from the words that are printed. In the new environment owing a document will not be problem for the library because the user will pay for its uses.

1. **Networking:** A particular digital library can provide the link to any other resources of other digital library very easily thus a seamlessly integrated resource sharing can be achieved.
2. **Space:** Whereas traditional libraries are limited by storage space, digital libraries have the potential to store much more information, simply because digital information requires very little physical space to contain them. When the library had no space for extension digitization is the only solution.
3. **No physical boundary:** The user of a digital library need not to go to the library physically, people from all over the world could gain access to the same information, as long as an Internet connection is available.
4. **Round the clock availability:** Digital libraries can be accessed at any time, 24 hours a day and 365 days of the year
5. **Structured approach:** Digital library provides access to much richer content in a more structured manner i.e. we can easily move from the catalog to the particular book then to a particular chapter and so on.
6. **Information retrieval:** The user is able to use any search term bellowing to the word or phrase of the entire collection. Digital library will provide very user friendly interfaces, giving click able access to its resources.
7. **Preservation and conservation:** An exact copy of the original can be made any number of times without any degradation in quality.
8. **Cost** - The cost of maintaining a digital library is much lower than that of a traditional library. A traditional library must spend large sums of money paying for staff, book maintains, rent, and additional books. Digital libraries do away with these fees.

Disadvantages of the Digital Library

The computer viruses, lack of standardization for digitized information, quick degrading properties of digitized material, different display standard of digital product and its associated problem, health hazard nature of the radiation from monitor etc. makes digital libraries at times handicap.

1. **Efficiency:** - With the much larger volume of digital information, finding the right material for a specific task becomes increasingly difficult.
2. **Environment:** - Digital libraries cannot reproduce the environment of a traditional library. Many people also find reading printed material to be easier than reading material on a computer screen.
3. **Copyright:** - Digitization violates the copy right law as the thought content of one author can be freely transfer by other without his acknowledgement. So One difficulty to overcome for digital libraries is the way to distribute information. How does a digital library distribute information at will while protecting the copyright of the author?
4. **Speed of access:** - As more and more computer are connected to the Internet its speed of access reasonably decreasing. If new technology will not evolve to solve the problem then in near future Internet will be full of error messages.
5. **Band width:** - Digital library will need high band for transfer of multimedia resources but the band width is decreasing day by day due to its over utilization.

6. **Preservation:** - Due to technological developments, a digital library can rapidly become out-of-date and its data may become inaccessible.
7. **Initial cost is high:** - The infrastructure cost of digital library i.e. the cost of hardware, software; leasing communication circuit is generally very high.

Conclusion

Digital libraries are not going to replace the physical existence of document completely but no doubt to meet the present demand, to satisfy the non local user digitization must be introduced so that at least libraries becomes of hybrid nature. The initial cost of digitization is high but experiment shows that once digitization is introduced then the cost to manage this collection will be cheaper than that of any traditional library. Day by day the cost of digitization is decreasing, the online publication is increasing, the needs of user are shifting towards a different environment so it's needless to say that after one or two years my library or your library will go to be digitized so it's the pick time to all informational and library professional that they geared themselves to take the challenge.

References

1. Ansari, Mehtab Alam (2003) Digital libraries: needs, technology and benefit, ILA Bulletin , 38(3), pp. 22-26.
2. Baecker, R., & Buxton, W. (1987). A historical and intellectual perspective. In R. Baecker & W. Buxton, Readings in Human-Computer Interaction: A multidisciplinary approach (pp. 41-54). San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann. 50
3. Baecker, R., Grudin, J., Buxton, W., & Greenberg, S. (1995). A historical and intellectual perspective. In R. Baecker, J. Grudin, W. Buxton, & S. Greenberg, Readings in Human-Computer Interaction: Toward the Year 2000 (pp. 35-47). San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann.
4. Baecker, J. Grudin, W. Buxton, & S. Greenberg, Readings in Human-Computer Interaction: Toward the Year 2000 (pp. 35-47). San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann.
5. Bagozzi, R.P., Davis, F.D., & Warshaw, P.R. (1992). Development and test of a theory of technological learning and usage. Human Relations, 45, 7, 660-686.
6. Banerjee, Swapna and Chakrabarty, Biplab (1999), Digital libraries: some issues and perspective, ILA Bulletin 34(3-4), October 1998 to March 1999, pp. 60-63.
7. Banker, R.D., & Kaufmann, R.J. (2004). The evolution of research on Information Systems: A fiftieth-year survey of the literature in Management Science. Management science, 50, 3, 281-298.
8. Bannon, L. (1991). From human factors to human actors: The role of psychology and human-computer interaction studies in system design. In J. Greenbaum & M. Kyng (Eds.), Design at Work (pp. 25-44). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
9. Bardini, T. (2000). Bootstrapping: Douglas Engelbart, coevolution, and the origins of personal computing. Stanford University.
10. Barnard, P. (1991). Bridging between basic theories and the artifacts of human-computer interaction. In J.M. Carroll (Ed.), Designing interaction: Psychology at the human-computer interface (pp. 103-127). Cambridge University Press.

11. Bewley, W.L., Roberts, T.L., Schroit, D. & Verplank, W.L. (1983). Human factors testing in the design of Xerox's 8010 —Starll office workstation. Proceedings CHI'83, pp. 72-77. New York: ACM.
12. Blackwell, A. (2006). The reification of metaphor as a design tool. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction*, 13, 4, pp. 490-530.
13. Burke, C. (2007). History of information science. In Cronin, B. (Ed.), *Annual review of information science and technology* 41, pp. 3-53. ASIST.
14. Cyric, Jiji, Deshmukh, G.R. and Rajalakshmi(2002) , Digitizationof libraries: in modern era, *ILA Bulletin* 38(3) pp.68-73.
15. Dyson, F. (1979). *Disturbing the universe*. New York: Harper & Row.
16. Dhaka, R.P.S. and Arora, Kamlesh (1995), Electronic libraries: A myth or a reality, *Annals of library science and documentation*.42(4). pp.152-59.
17. Fidel, R. (2010). Human information interaction: an ecological approach to information behavior. Under review. pp. 52.
18. Grudin, J. (2006). Human Factors, CHI, and MIS. In P. Zhang & D. Galletta (eds.), *HCI in MIS (I): Foundations*. Armonk, NY: M.E. Sharpe.
19. Grudin, J. (2008). A moving target: The evolution of human-computer interaction. In A. Sears & J. Jacko (Eds.), *Handbook of Human-Computer Interaction*, pp. 1-24. CRC Press.
20. Grudin, J. (2010). Technology, conferences and community. *Communications of the ACM*.
21. Hertzfeld, A. (2005). *Revolution in the valley: The insanely great story of how the Mac was made*. Sebastapol, CA: O'Reilly Media.
22. Hiltzik, M.A. (1999). *Dealers of lightning: Xerox PARC and the dawn of the computer age*. New York: HarperCollins.
23. Khan, Shakeel Ahmad, Khayat, Roshan and Yunus, Mohad (2003), Digital libraries: the present scenario, *ILA Bulletin* 39(2) pp.3-7.
24. Koteswara Rao, M (2003), Digital Libraries: Challenges, Opportunities and Implications, paper presented at SIS-2004 Conference 22-23 Januray 2004, Madras.
25. Kumar, Bhuvan and Reddy, V.Sreeniuas (2003), Digital library use: a case study of NIT library, Waraangal, *ILA Bulletin* 39(2) pp.40-45.
26. Markoff, J. (2005). *What the dormouse said: How the 60s counterculture shaped the personal computer*. London: Viking.
27. Meister, D. (1999). *The History of Human Factors and Ergonomics*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
28. Meister D. (2005). HFES history. In *HFES 2005-2006 directory and yearbook*, 2-3. Santa Monica: Human Factors and Ergonomic Society.
29. Myers, B.A. (1998). A brief history of human computer interaction technology. *ACM interactions*, 5, 2, pp. 44-54.
30. Perlman, G., Green, G.K. & Wogalter, M.S. (1995). *Human Factors perspectives on Human-Computer Interaction*. Santa Monica: Human Factors and Ergonomics Society.

31. Ravichandra Rao I.K. and Suma P. (1996), Digital libraries, challenge and issues, Digitized information paper presented at the SIS-96, 18-20 January 1996, Bangalore, (Eds) T.B.Rajasekhar, I.K. Ravichandra Rao and N.V. Satyanarayana, pp.185-195.
32. Roscoe, S.N. (1997). *The adolescence of engineering psychology*. Santa Monica, CA: Human Factors and Ergonomics Society.
33. Shackel, B. (1997). Human-computer interaction: whence and whither? *Journal of ASIS*, 48, 11, pp. 970–986.
34. Taylor, F.W. (1911). *The principles of scientific management*. New York: Harper.
35. Zhang, P., Li, N., Scialdone, M.J. & Carey, J. (2009). The intellectual advancement of Human-Computer Interaction Research: A critical assessment of the MIS Literature. *Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction*, 1, 3, 55-107.
36. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_library
37. <http://scholar.lib.vt.edu/DLI2/defineDL.html>
38. <http://www.clir.org/pubs/issues/issues04.html#dlf>

SALEK CHAND holds B. Com, and M. Com; B. Lib. Inf. Sc. and M. Lib. Info. Sc. From University of Delhi, is currently working as Library & Information Officer and Head, Library & Resource Centre of the Election Commission of India, New Delhi. Prior to that he has served as Sr. Documentation Officer and Head, National Documentation Centre of National Institute of Health and Family Welfare, New Delhi and Librarian in Ministry of Water Resources Delhi and as Documentation Officer in Central Road Research Institute, Delhi. He has 26 years experience at different capacity. Mr. Salek Chand has contributed more than 36 papers and published at national and international level. He has a credit of publishing two books reviews and also serving as a reviewer of many Journals. During his academic carrier, he conducted various training courses, seminars and projects. He is recipient of Best Coordinator Award from ACCMAN Instt. of Management, NOIDA; Best Conference Coordinator Award from Aggarwal College Ballabhgarh, HARYANA, Best Librarian Award form IDLA & GACL, Indore, MP and Int'l Travel Award from SLA, USA. He widely traveled with different assignments in Philippines, Malaysia, Singapore, China, Australia, Greece, Thailand, Japan, South Korea, USA and UK. He is actively associated with various professional bodies such as Indian Library Association; Medical Library Association of India; Ranganathan Research Circle, SALIS, LPA, SLP, CSSW, MANLIBNET, SLA Asian Chapter, etc. Presently acting as Secretary, SLA The Asian Chapter; Secretary, Library Professionals Association; President, CSSW and Executive Board Member of DELNET.

M. Natarajan is currently working as Editor of Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research. Worked as Head, Education & Training Division, Senior Principal Scientist, NISCAIR. Joined **INSDOC, Chennai on 16th Sep 1981** and has more than 31 years of experience. Acting as IGNOU Co-ordinator at NISCAIR New Delhi. Worked in almost all the divisions of NISCAIR (Ex-INSDOC). Worked for one year in **National Science Digital Library (NSDL)** project. Given lectures for the **Short term training courses**. Also organised **five UGC sponsored Refresher Course for Librarians** and acted as a **Co-ordinator** and delivered lectures for 129 librarians from all over India. Many Projects / dissertations have been guided to students from MLIS, MPhil, PGDLAN and AIS. Worked as Scientist-in-charge of INSDOC Chennai and Bangalore. **Life Member** of many Professional Associations like MALA, SIS, SALIS, IASLIC, ILA, MULISANET, AIS and President of Library Professionals Association. Editorial Board Member of six journals. Published more than 150 papers in national / international journals, conferences and Festschrift volumes. Also reviewer for 4 journals.

Dr. Rama Nand Malviya is Librarian and Coordinator of Lingaya's Journal of Professional Studies at the Lingaya's University, Nachauli, Old Faridabad- Jasana Road, Faridabad, Haryana. He received his M.A. in Economics, MBA- HRM and Master of Library and Information Science, Ph. D. from Jiwaji University, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh and has been associated with the field of Research and Library and Information Science for more than two decades. He has worked in National Council of Economic Research (NCAER) New Delhi, Indian Institute of Public Administration (IIPA) New Delhi, IPRA New Delhi, Indian Social Institute, New Delhi and Institute for Integrated Learning Management Academy of Higher Learning (IILM-AHL) Greater Noida. He has published four books and more than 45 papers in refereed Journals. He is member of all major Indian Library Association, Library Professional Association and has been acted as Rapporteur General, Keynote speaker and Chairman of the session in various National and International Conference. He has organized various national and International Conferences. He has guided a number of Students of M.L.I.Sc., PGDLAN and visiting professor Ph. D. Guide in various universities.

₹ 1095

ISBN 978-93-5196-852-2

LIBRARY PROFESSIONALS ASSOCIATION (LPA)
M-25, First Floor, No. 103, Lado Sarai, New Delhi - 110030
www.lpaindia.in